

Serum Corticosterone Levels Following Exposure to Stressors of Varying Nature and Stress-Induced Withdrawal in Rats

*Nwogueze BC,¹ Aloamaka CP,² Igweh JC²

ABSTRACT

The present study was designed to examine serum Corticosterone levels following exposure to stressors of varying nature and stress-induced withdrawal effect in female Wistar rats. Three (3) stress models were used to induce stress in the animals. The study was divided into two sets of experiments; the first aspect utilized 168 rats randomly distributed into 28 groups. Based on the outcome of the unit one study, 60 rats randomly distributed into 10 groups were utilized for unit two experiment to estimate the impact of weekly stressor withdrawal up to three weeks. Data were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Analysis was performed using ANOVA statistic. Results obtained from the first set of experiments revealed that serum levels of Corticosterone were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in rats by exposing them to different stressors and this was dependent on the duration of exposure to stress; minimal increase was observed within the first-week exposure to stress, the level peaked within the second week, but by the third week the level returned to about the control level. Results from the unit two study revealed that withdrawal of the different nature of stressors weekly for up to three weeks did not significantly alter the serum level of Corticosterone in the stressed rats. In conclusion, the return of the serum level of Corticosterone, at the end of three weeks reflects adaptive changes suggesting an optimal physiologic adjustment to the stressful conditions. Withdrawal of stressors for three weeks may not have been responsible for activation of the mechanism for the reversal of the adaptive change.

Keywords: Stress, Stressor, Biomarker, Corticosterone, Withdrawal, Wistar

INTRODUCTION

Stress is an integral part of our lives. Every living organism experiences some form of stress during its lifetime. The current approaches to measure stress across many physiological systems include; self-reports, measures of effect, measures of stressor exposure and use of biomarkers. Biomarkers can help to both characterize stress objectively and measure the stress response. They are vital in quantifying stress and have immense diagnostic and prognostic value. A biomarker is a characteristic which can be objectively measured and evaluated as an indicator of a biological state. The term biomarker as perceived by the National Institutes of Health [NIH] is "a characteristic that is objectively evaluated and measured as an indicator of normal biological and pathogenic processes or pharmacological responses relating to a therapeutic intervention".¹

Neuroendocrine factors are effective as biomarkers for stress as they serve as the first to respond to a given stressor. Stress threatens homeostasis by inducing the release of hormones such as; Adrenaline and Noradrenaline, along with glucocorticoids, and the fight-or-flight response is initiated under acute stress. Hormones generally are chemical messengers that travel far and wide in the body to transmit information and trigger specific responses from cell groups and tissues.² In other words, they are like keys that turn on or off the switches throughout the body. Once hormones arrive at their target sites they interact with receptor molecules to deliver their messages by forming a hormone-receptor complex.²

The various examples of neuroendocrine biomarkers of chronic stress currently in use include; Corticosterone, Dehydroepiandrosterone, Adrenaline, Noradrenaline, Dopamine, and Aldosterone. Some studies identified plasma Adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and corticosterone hormone concentrations as important stress biomarkers.³ It is important to note that ACTH is elevated under chronic stress which induces an elevation in the levels

College of Health Sciences,¹ Department of Physiology, Evangel University, Akaeze, Abakiliki, Ebony State. Department of Human Physiology,² Delta State University, Abraka.

*Corresponding author: bukasono123@gmail.com

of Corticosterone and depletions of other glucocorticoids.⁴ These hormones increase locomotor activity, blood pressure, and carbohydrate metabolism while suppressing immune function, growth, and reproductive systems. They also affect multiple brain regions and neurotransmitter systems, resulting in multiple behavioural consequences.⁵ Chronic marked elevations of stress hormones can be deleterious for organisms in general and especially for reproductive functions.^{6,7}

Corticosterone is a glucocorticoid synthesized by the adrenal cortex which has immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory effects. It is also involved in the conversion of stored fats and proteins into carbohydrates.⁸ In situations of chronic or excessive stress, however, these hormones are overproduced and can cause physical harm.⁹ Corticosterone is a critical biomarker of stress can be measured from urine, saliva or serum. In explaining the dynamics behind the regulation of stress responses in rodents, it is important to consider the serum corticosterone level as a major glucocorticoid.¹⁰ More so, measurements of this hormone directly captures the status of hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis function, which is a mediator of many secondary outcomes - its dysfunction can lead to disease.¹⁰

Re-establishment of homeostasis is achieved by evoking adaptive responses leading to a coping strategy. Such coping mechanisms have an adaptive value in a stressful situation for all living organisms.¹¹ Numerous mechanisms are responsible for understanding the impact of stress exposure on Corticosterone levels released by the adrenal glands in response to HPA axis activation. Stressor withdrawal suggests a

direct biological link with stress-induced Corticosterone levels as manifested in the biochemical, cellular and behavioural in response to establishing homeostatic balance in the internal milieu of experimental animals. Withdrawal of stressors could induce resilience to stress; hence this study examines serum Corticosterone levels after exposure to stressors of varying nature and stress-induced withdrawal in rats.¹²

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal procurement

Female Wistar rats within the ages of 12-14 weeks weighing between 120-180g were procured and used in experimenting. The animals were procured from Emma Maria Diagnostic and Research Laboratory and were kept in the animal facility of the Department of Human Physiology, Delta State University, Abraka in collective cages (six rats per cage), in a temperature-controlled room ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) with proper darkness-light cycles (12/12 hours photoperiod). The animals were fed with a regular diet and water unrestricted. All experiments with animals were performed following the approved guidelines for animal handling by the Bioethics Research Committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka (Permit number: REC/FBMC/DELSU/19/58).

Experimental group

In the first set of the experiments, 168 animals were randomly distributed into 28 groups while for the second experiment, 60 Wistar rats were randomly distributed into 10 groups. Each unit comprised of control and experimental groups as described in Tables 1 and 2 below:

Table 1: Experiments on Stress-induced Corticosterone level determination in female Wistar rats

Groups	Description	No. of Rats
Group 1	Control female Wistar rats	6 rats
Group 2 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Restraint stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 1 week.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 3 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Mirrored stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 1 week.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 4 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Predator intruder stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 1 week.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 5 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Restraint stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 2 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 6 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Mirrored stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 2 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 7 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Predator intruder stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 2 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 8 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Restraint stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 3 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 9 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Mirrored stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 3 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 10 ^{a,b,c}	Female Wistar rats exposed to Predator intruder stressor at the rate of 1, 3 and 5hours per day for 3 weeks.	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
	Total	168

a,b,c= indicates the groups for week 1, 2 and 3.

Table 2: Stressor Withdrawal Experiment

Groups	Description	No. of Rats
Group 1	Control non-pregnant female Wistar rats	6 rats
Group 2 ^{a,b,c}	Non-pregnant Wistar rats exposed to different (3) stressors at 3 hours per day for 3 weeks, after which the stressors were withdrawn for 1 week	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 3 ^{a,b,c}	Non-pregnant Wistar rats exposed to different (3) stressors at a rate of 3 hours per day for 3 weeks, after which the stressors were withdrawn for 2 weeks	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
Group 4 ^{a,b,c}	Non-pregnant Wistar rats exposed to different (3) stressors at 3 hours per day for 3 weeks, after which the stressors were withdrawn for 3 weeks	6 rats x 3 stressors = 18
	Total	60

a,b,c= indicates the groups for week 1, 2 and 3

Stress induction

Stressors of three (3) different natures were employed to induce stress in the Wistar rats as described below:

1. *Procedures for restraint stress model*

The female Wistar rats were allowed into separate cylindrical plastic tubes (inner diameter, 5.7cm, length 20.3cm) to induce essentially physical stress, adopting the

2. *Procedures for mirrored stress model*

For mirrored stress testing, animals

were placed in the mirrored chamber for a variable duration depending on the research protocol. The Mirrored chamber consisted of a wooden compartment measuring 42 x 42 x 42cm cube. The chamber was made of three separate compartments, with each having three mirrored walls and an opaque black coloured wall. The experimental procedure for mirrored stressor was designed for studying anxiety stress in the Wistar rats following the methods of Lamberty and Gower.¹⁴

3. **Procedures for Predator Intruder Stress Model**

The test apparatus comprised of a box with three (3) partitions measuring 25 x 13 x 32cm at each side of its length, with each row of the partitions being separated by a passage. The wall of the partitions forming the passage was made up of wire gauze while the partitions contain the rats to be stressed; meanwhile, an aggressive cat is contained in the passage. The chamber was employed to induce psychosocial stress on the animals adopting the methods of McGregor *et al.*¹⁵ The stress-induced was considered essentially psychological with minimal physical component.¹⁶

Stress withdrawal experiment

Based on the findings of the results of the unit 1 experiment presented in Figure 1, 2 and 3 respectively, the animals used for unit 2 experiment was utilized for stressor withdrawal study. The non-pregnant Wistar rats exposed to different (3) stressors at a rate of three hours per day for three weeks, after which the stressors were withdrawn on weekly intervals for three weeks (week 1, 2 and 3 respectively), thereafter the serum levels of serum Corticosterone were assessed.

Sample collection and biochemical investigation

At the end of a given experimental period for the different groups of rats exposed to the various kinds of stressors, the animals were killed by cervical dislocation. Blood samples were collected from the Wistar rats by cardiac puncture, with the aid of a sterile syringe and needle into sample containers for biochemical investigations. The serum was separated by centrifugation (1700 ×g, 10 min, 4°C) and corticosterone hormone assay was done using the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit.

Statistical analysis

Data were expressed as Mean±SEM. The analysis was performed using ANOVA, and Fischer's Least Square Difference for the post-hoc test. A P-value <0.05 was adopted for the significance level.

RESULTS

Changes in serum Corticosterone levels following exposure to different stressors

Figure 1 below revealed that exposure of the rats to restraint and mirror stressors for 1 week did not significantly alter serum levels of corticosterone when compared with the control level. This was irrespective of the rate of exposure. For the predator intruder stressor, exposure of the rats to the stressor at the rate of one hour or five hours per day significantly ($p<0.05$) increased serum corticosterone level beyond the control level, but this was not the case for exposure at the rate of three hours per day. The same trend was observed for exposure at three hours per day but the difference between the corticosterone level induced by predator intruder stressor and that induced by exposure to restraint or mirror stressors was not significant.

Figure 1: Effect of Stress on the Corticosterone Level Rats after Exposure to Different Stressors for 1, 3, or 5 Hours Per Day for 1 Week (n=6).

* = significant when compared to control

c = significant when compared to predator intruder stressor

Figure 2 below shows that exposure of rats to restraint stressor cause significant ($p<0.05$) increase in the level of serum corticosterone irrespective of the rate of exposure, when compared to control the level of the hormone. Concerning predator intruder stressor, significant ($p<0.05$) increase in the level of corticosterone was observed when the rats were exposed to the stressor at the rate of one hour per day and three hours per day, though the level of the hormone when exposed to five hours per day was still greater than the control level (but was not significant).

Exposure of the rats to mirror stressor did not cause significant alterations in the serum level of Corticosterone when compared to control the level of Corticosterone, and this was irrespective of the rate of exposure to the stressor; though there was a slight increase in the level of the hormone in the case of exposure at one hour and three hours per day.

Figure 2: Effect of Stress on the Corticosterone Level of Rats after Exposure to Different Stressors for 1, 3, or 5 Hours Per Day for 2 Weeks (n=6).

* = significant when compared to control
a = significant when compared to restraint stressor;

Figure 3 revealed that the responses to stress following exposure to the 3 stressors studied to a large extent assumed the pattern observed when the rats were exposed to the stressors for 1week. In the case of the one hour and three hours exposure per week, the serum Corticosterone levels of the rats were not significantly different from the control level, and this was irrespective of the nature of stressor used in inducing stress in the rats. The observation was the same for stress-induced following exposing the rats at the rate of five hours per day to restraint and mirror stressors for three weeks. The Corticosterone levels in the stressed rats were not significantly different from the control levels. However, the predator intruder stressor caused a significantly ($p < 0.05$) greater serum Corticosterone level in the rats when compared to the control level and the levels following exposure to restraint and mirror stressors.

Figure 3: Effect of Stress on the Corticosterone Level of Rats after Exposure to Different Stressors for 1, 3, or 5 Hours Per Day for 3 Weeks (n=6).

* = significant when compared to control
c = significant when compared to predator intruder stressor

Changes in serum corticosterone levels following stressor withdrawal

Figure 4 below shows the effect of stressor withdrawal on serum corticosterone levels in female Wistar rats following exposure to stressors at the rate of three hours per day for three weeks. It was observed that exposure of the rats to the respective stressors for three weeks did not significantly alter serum Corticosterone level in the stressed rats. Also, the withdrawal of the respective stressors weekly did not significantly alter the level of serum Corticosterone.

Figure 4: Effect of Weekly Stressor Withdrawal on Serum Corticosterone Level in Rats Exposed to the Respective Stressors at 3 Hours Per Day, and for 3 Weeks (n=6).

* =level of the hormone when the rats were stressed (3 hours per day, 3 weeks).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, Wistar rats were stressed by exposure to restraint stressor, mirror chamber stressor and resident predator intruder stressor and it was observed that the responses of the rats to the different stressors varied. Exposure of rats to the three stressors for one week caused significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in serum corticosterone level only for predator intruder stressor following exposure for one hour and five hours per day (Figure 1). The resident intruder stressor is associated with depressive-like behaviour in experimental situations. Considering the nature of the intruder, in this case, cats (predator), the rats are bound to experience great fear, making it much different from the mirror stressor.¹⁷

The results obtained from the first experiments showed that serum level of corticosterone revealed minimal increase above the control level within the first week of exposure to stressors, the level peaked within the second week of exposure to stressors, but by the third week the level returned to about the control level. This observation agrees with the conclusion of Selye and Fortier that stress response depends on the intensity and duration of the stressful condition. But the fact that serum level of corticosterone returned to about the control level by the third week of exposure of the rats to stressors will suggest that some adaptive changes had taken place in the rats thus suppressing the mechanism for enhancing corticosterone level.¹⁸

But the fact that serum level of corticosterone returned to about the control level by the third week of exposure of the rats to stressors will suggest that some adaptive changes had taken place in the rats thus suppressing the mechanism for enhancing corticosterone level. According to Michael *et al.*¹⁹ rats respond to stressors by increasing their serum glucocorticoids level. The findings are in line with the study by Mohammed *et al.*²⁰ who showed that acute exposure to restraint stressor significantly increased serum Corticosterone levels in male rats. Also, Cho *et al.* made a similar observation when he found elevated Corticosterone levels in female Wistar rats exposed to restraint stressor for 1hour, 30

minutes. This effect of stress has been associated with a cascade of neurohormonal events which occurs chiefly by activation of the HPA axis.²¹

This study revealed that exposure of the rats to the respective stressors at the rate of three hours per day for three weeks did not significantly alter serum corticosterone level in the stressed rats (Figure 4). Also, the withdrawal every week for up to three weeks did not significantly alter the serum level of corticosterone in the stressed rats. This observation could be the reason why Stankiewicz *et al.* pointed out that the elicited responses to stress and reversal may differ depending on the type of stress and hormonal state of the individual.²² The limbic HPA-axis is the primary circuit that is involved in initiation, regulation and termination of a stress response, with the brain areas involved in stress control and response being similar.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the biomarker analyzed (serum corticosterone concentrations) revealed minimal increase within the first week of exposure to stress, however, the level peaked within the second week with the predator intruder stressor producing more deleterious effect when compared to the other stressors, but by the third week, the level of serum corticosterone returned to about the control level which is reflective of optimal physiologic adjustment to the stressful conditions. Meanwhile, the stepwise withdrawal of stressors for up to the 3weeks produced no significant change in the serum levels of corticosterone, hence, suggesting that the withdrawal may not have been long enough for activation of the mechanism for the reversal of the adaptive change which had taken place.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The results from this study have necessitated the need for further evaluation of the physiological basis of stress-induced serum corticosterone alterations with a proper investigation of oxidative stress levels and histoarchitectural integrity of the tissues of female Wistar rats.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors acknowledge that there is no conflict of interest for this article.

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